

The landscape of preference signaling for AI training

The launch of powerful AI systems developed by large tech corporations has shifted the power balance between internet creators and those corporations. A series of efforts is underway to restore balance through contracts, licenses, and other technical signals for data crawlers. This article maps the most visible efforts to introduce preference signaling on the public web: Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) AI Preferences, Creative Commons Preference Signals, Code Commons AI Preference Attachment for Software Projects, Real Simple License, CloudFlare AI Crawl, and the TDM-AI Protocol.

Technical, legal, and cultural landscape

If you post content online, you've likely wondered who controls where your work ends up when AI models scrape the entire internet. For years, the answer relied on copyright law and using blocking tools like robots.txt to tell bots to go away.

The accumulation of data to feed into the modern AI machines of OpenAI, Google, Anthropic, Microsoft, Meta, Amazon, etc., to produce “[stochastic parrots](#)” and “[plagiarism machines](#)” has changed the minds of large publishers, small independent authors, and many individual content producers alike.

Blocking mechanisms are becoming more popular to the point that [research by the Data Provenance Initiative](#) found that between 2023 and 2024, over 45% of the publicly available sources of the popular dataset C4 were restricted to use for AI training.

Publicly available datasets derived from web scraping have historically supported advancements in AI research. The commercial launch of widely available products raised ethical concerns about privacy, consent, and data ownership. One central problem is the unbalanced power dynamic between a few extremely large AI companies and many content creators and rights owners.

The lack of a universal, standardized, and granular system for content creators and rightsholders to express, communicate, and condition their preferences regarding the automated consumption and use of their digital content at internet scale.

The [Open Source Initiative](#) and [Open Future Foundation](#) identified in a [2024 paper](#) six critical focus areas to address the public concerns, increase data sharing, and protect knowledge commons:

1. Data preparation and provenance: Establishing robust standards for data collection, classification, anonymization, and metadata to ensure quality and

- traceability.
2. Preference signaling and licensing: Developing mechanisms like opt-out frameworks and social licenses to allow rights holders and communities to control data use.
 3. Data stewards and custodians: Strengthening roles for data stewardship, including intermediary institutions that facilitate data sharing while ensuring ethical governance.
 4. Environmental sustainability: Promoting practices that reduce the environmental impact of AI through shared datasets and efficient training methods.
 5. Reciprocity and compensation: Implementing mechanisms that ensure value generated from shared data is equitably distributed, particularly to marginalized communities.
 6. Policy interventions: Advocating for public policies that mandate data transparency, incentivize data sharing, and support the creation of open datasets.

Limitations of robots.txt

The Robots Exclusion Protocol (REP, defined in [RFC9309](#), also known as robots.txt) was [designed for search crawlers](#). When it comes to AI, the protocol puts content owners into a weak position. Assuming that the crawlers are correctly identifying themselves, the protocol relies on bots' owners to design them for specific and narrow purposes in order for the Allow/Disallow directives to make sense. Google, for example, has a bot designated for search and one for AI training: content owners can choose to block one and allow another. But GoogleBOT, the search crawler, is also used for summarizing content, a practice that not all publishers approve of. Google could develop a different bot for summarized content, and so could anybody else interested in building an AI. Even in an ideal world of only well-behaving, clearly-identified bots, their proliferation would become a problem for the internet infrastructure.

Ultimately, the protocol ties content owners to the business interests of the AI companies and their goodwill. The choice of Allow/Disallow based on the existence of narrowly-scoped bots forces rights-owners into a position that doesn't support a mutually beneficial ecosystem.

The [REP](#) "applies to services that provide resources that clients can access through URIs," limiting the application of rules to domains and individual files at the time of the harvest.

Progress in preference signaling and licensing

A range of cross-sector initiatives is emerging to mediate the relationship between content creators and the massive-scale crawlers powering AI models, seeking to replace ad-hoc scraping with controllable, sustainable protocols. They're building a digital "social contract" for text and data mining for AI.

These initiatives operate in the context of ongoing legal debate regarding the scope and applicability of statutory text and data mining (TDM) exceptions, particularly whether such exceptions, as provided for in EU and national copyright laws, extend to the training of generative AI systems. The takeaways show that the future of content control is far more complex than a simple "allow" or "deny."

What follows is a curated overview of the most significant initiatives hoping to restore a balance between the interests of AI developers and those of creators and rights holders.

[IETF AI Preferences \(AiPref\) Working Group](#)

[Text and Data Mining AI protocol](#)

[Creative Commons Signals](#)

[Really Simple Licensing \(RSL\)](#)

[AI Preference Attachment for Software Projects](#)

[Cloudflare AI Crawl Control](#)

IETF AI PREFERENCES (AiPref) WORKING GROUP STANDARD BLOCKS FOR SIGNALING	TEXT AND DATA MINING AI PROTOCOL (TDM-AI) PERSISTENT ASSET BINDING	CREATIVE COMMONS SIGNALS (CC SIGNALS) RECIPROCITY-BASED DATA STEWARDSHIP
REALLY SIMPLE LICENSING (RSL) AI BOT & SCRAPER LICENSING	AI PREFERENCE ATTACHMENT FOR SOFTWARE PROJECTS FILE-LEVEL CODE INTENT ATTACHMENT	CLOUDFLARE AI CRAWL CONTROL DOMAIN-LEVEL FIREWALL & MONETIZATION

ACTIVELY DEVELOPED
 STALLED
 GENERALLY AVAILABLE

IETF AI Preferences (AiPref) Working Group

The IETF AI Preferences (AiPref) Working Group is developing standardized building blocks that allow content creators to signal how their data should be used by automated systems. The work being done by this group is referenced by Creative Commons, Really Simple Licensing, CodeCommons, and TDM-AI: all have a reference to IETF's vocabulary. While AiPref handles the expression of usage intent, it is expected to liaise with the [Web Bot Authentication](#) (webbotauth) Working Group. The webbotauth scope is to create a complementary security layer by standardizing methods for cryptographically authenticating automated clients, allowing site operators to reliably verify the identity of the specific entities or AI products accessing their resources. At the [last webbotauth WG meeting](#), the chair decided to go back to discussing context rather than elaborate a detailed proposal.

Core deliverables

The group is focused on three primary technical pillars:

1. Shared vocabulary: A standards-track document defining terms for machine reuse. As of [draft-ietf-ai-pref-vocab-05](#) (released on Dec 2025), the scope is focused on two primary categories:
 - Foundation model production: Using assets to train or fine-tune large-scale models.
 - Search: Using assets in applications that direct users back to the source via excerpts and links.
2. Attachment mechanisms: Specifications for [associating these preferences with assets](#) via:
 - Robots Exclusion Protocol (robots.txt): For location-based/path-based rules.
 - HTTP Response Headers (Content-Usage): For unit-based or per-request preferences.
3. Reconciliation methods: Protocols to resolve conflicting preferences expressed for the same asset. These are defined in section 5 of the AI Pref Vocabulary.

Key points

The *Vocabulary* version 0.5 defines a standardized language for content creators to express how automated systems may use their digital assets, specifically focusing on the training and use of AI models. The first draft (version 00, [authored by Paul Keller](#), Open Future Foundation) was picked among a few [other early drafts](#). Version 00 focused on the broad framework of text and data mining, making a distinction between general-purpose AI training and generative AI. Version 0.5 represents a significant narrowing of scope to overcome previous stalls in consensus, defining only two primary categories of use: Foundation Model Production, which covers using assets to train or fine-tune large machine-learning models, and Search, which involves using assets in applications that direct users to original locations through verbatim excerpts and reference links. The terms like *Automated Processing* and categories related to inference-time use that were present in earlier iterations lacked multi-stakeholder agreement. The vocabulary utilizes a data model where recipients associate these categories with one of three preference values: "allowed," "disallowed," or "unknown". The values are mapped to technical labels, train-ai and search, within a machine-readable serialization format. The draft

specifies that these signals do not create new legal rights or prohibitions and may be ignored in specific contexts justified by recognized priorities such as accessibility, education, safety, or public interest.

The *Attachment* version 0.4, published on October 28, 2025, specifies standardized methods for signaling usage preferences during content acquisition via HTTP. Formally updating [RFC 9309](#), the draft defines two primary mechanisms for technical expression: the Robots Exclusion Protocol (robots.txt) for location-based preferences and a new HTTP Content-Usage header for unit-based preferences. These tools allow servers to communicate specific directives, such as `train-ai=n` or `train-ai=y`, to automated crawlers at either the site-wide or individual asset level. While this version focuses on the conveyance of preference strings, it does not define the usage categories themselves nor provide a mechanism for technical enforcement, noting that the legal effect of these signals depends on the governing jurisdiction.

The IETF AI Preferences protocol resolves conflicting usage signals by applying a "most restrictive preference" rule. Under this reconciliation method, if an application obtains multiple statements of preference for the same digital asset, it evaluates each usage category individually: if any statement indicates that a use is disallowed, the resulting preference is disallowed. If no statement disallows the use but at least one explicitly allows it, the result is allowed; otherwise, the preference is considered unknown. This approach differs from the standard Robots Exclusion Protocol, which typically defaults to the most permissive rule for crawling. However, the standard explicitly notes that these technical signals can be overridden by express contractual agreements or specific legal arrangements between parties.

Who is behind it

The technical direction is shaped by a mix of "Big Tech" engineers, public interest advocates, and academic researchers.

Lead authors & editors

- Martin Thomson (Mozilla): Primary editor for Vocabulary and Attachment drafts.
- Paul Keller (Open Future): Lead author of the Vocabulary draft; focuses on public interest.
- Gary Illyes (Google): Lead author of the Attachment draft; expert on search crawling.

Key contributors to discussions

- [Mark Nottingham](#) (Cloudflare): Facilitator; focuses on HTTP semantics and normative implications.
- [Lila Bailey](#) (Internet Archive): Legal and policy perspective.
- [Thom Vaughan](#) (CommonCrawl): Legal and technical contributor.
- [Cullen Miller](#): Technical contributor.
- [Laurent Le Meur](#) (EDRLab): Contributor to digital asset standards.
- [Krishna Madhavan](#) (Microsoft): Active on GitHub regarding hierarchical structures.
- [Felix Reda](#) (GitHub): Expert on copyright and user rights.
- [Leonard Rosenthal](#) (Adobe): Standards expert (C2PA/IPTC).
- [Chris Needham](#) (BBC): Focuses on media metadata and platform T&Cs.
- [Orie Steele](#) (Transmute): Focuses on regulatory compliance (e.g., Article 4).

- [Michael Prorock](#) (mesur.io): Focuses on RAG and generative search boundaries.
- [Cooper Quintin](#) (EFF - "Coopdanger"): Focuses on quantified thresholds for foundation models.

Development status

The standard is currently a "Work in Progress" on the Standards Track. IETF's process started with birds of a feather discussion at IETF's meeting. Early drafts of the standard started circulating, i.e. [Tremate and Romm \(Cloudflare\)](#), [Farzaneh \(Digital Medusa\)](#), [Baley \(Internet Archive\) and Levy \(Norton Law\)](#), [Thom Vaughan \(CommonCrawl\)](#), [Silver \(Advance\)](#) and [Altanai \(Cisco\)](#). The working group was formed in 2024 and its charter was [approved in November 2025](#). The next in-person/remote meeting of the working group is scheduled for April 16 in Toronto ([details, including remote participation](#)).

The working group faces significant debate regarding the intersection of technical standards and legal frameworks:

- The usage vs. acquisition gap: RFC 9309 (robots.txt) was designed to manage acquisition (where a bot can go). AiPref attempts to regulate usage (how data is processed post-acquisition). Critics argue that using a 1995-era protocol for complex AI training nuances creates a technical mismatch.
- Regulatory entanglement: There is concern that the [EU AI Act's GPAI Code of Practice](#), which references "subsequent versions" of RFC 9309, could transform voluntary IETF technical standards into mandatory legal requirements.
- Implementation burden: Small site owners may struggle to maintain exhaustive lists of AI agents, while publishers fear that standardizing these signals might inadvertently limit existing copyright exceptions or fair use rights.
- Lack of nuance: There are [concerns](#) about mapping the rights of media owners in the preferences, including copyright and trademarks, while leaving space for competition.

According to the IETF's schedule, the working group is expected to submit the RFC for consideration to the Internet Engineering Steering Group (IESG) by August 2026. The publication of the RFC is expected later in 2026 or early 2027.

Relevant Links

- **IETF Datatracker (Main Page):** [WG AiPref](#)
- **Public Mailing List:** [aipref@ietf.org Archives](#)
- **GitHub Repository:** [ietf-wg-aipref](#)
- **Vocabulary Draft:** [draft-ietf-aipref-vocab](#)
- **Attachment Draft:** [draft-ietf-aipref-attach](#)

Text and Data Mining AI protocol

The TDM-AI Protocol (TDM-AI) is a technical specification designed to be an attachment mechanism for digital content, allowing creators and rightsholders to persistently and verifiably

attach machine-readable usage preferences to their assets.

This system addresses the challenge of controlling automated processing by using technology that ensures that ownership, provenance, and metadata information remain tamper-proof and persistently bound to the content, even if metadata or watermarks are removed from the content.

Instead of relying on file-level metadata or exclusions specified at the domain level, like `robots.txt`, the [TDM-AI protocol](#) tightly binds rightsholders' preferences to the media file, leveraging the [International Standard Content Code](#) (ISCC, ISO 24138:2024) and cryptographic credentials for identification and verifiability of the rights owners.

The TDM-AI protocol ensures a reliable method of identifying content that is robust to common problems such as the loss of embedded metadata, removal of watermarks or steganographic data, or other alterations or manipulations of content.

How ISCC identifiers work

ISCC identifiers are generated algorithmically from the content itself. Files including text, images, audio, and video are processed to build the identifier from a generic mix of content-derived, locality-sensitive, and similarity-preserving hashes generated from metadata and the content itself.

The ISCC does not have to be manually assigned, nor does it have to be carried around or embedded within the content because it can be calculated and verified by anyone: The content itself is the source and authority of the ISCC. The ISCC was originally designed to operate on a blockchain, but it seems to be increasingly developed to be used off-chain within a local content repository for internal processing or non-blockchain digital transactions.

The [ISCC Foundation](#) maintains the Python reference implementation of the ISCC core algorithms, [iscc-core](#). See the demo on [ISCC](#) website.

THE DNA OF YOUR DIGITAL CONTENT

Source: <https://iscc.io/>

How to identify the rights owners

TDM-AI relies on [Creator Credentials](#) to identify the rightsholders. Creator Credentials are based on the [W3C recommendation for cryptographically verifiable credentials](#). They provide a layer of trust by ensuring that machine-readable AI preferences are genuine and attributable to the legitimate rightsholders or content controllers. These credentials are the mechanism that allows attaching the preference declarations cryptographically to a proven identity rather than just being an unauthenticated informational claim.

The credentials are governed by a trust model that involves several technical and legal layers (see [CommonsDB project report](#)):

1. Identity confirmation: An issuer (such as Open Future in the prototype implementation, [CommonsDB](#)) verifies the identity of the Data Supplier or rightsholder before granting the credential.
2. Certified identity of the issuer: To establish a "trust chain," the issuer typically holds an [Advanced Certificate for Electronic Seal](#) issued by a Qualified Trust Service Provider (such as Halcom, in the case of CommonsDB) under the [eIDAS framework](#).
3. Binding keys: Once the identity is confirmed, the issuer provides a Verifiable Credential that binds a public key to the holder and officially states their role as an authorized party.
4. Signing declarations: The credential holder then uses their private cryptographic keys to

sign individual declarations. This links the rights information and metadata to a content-derived identifier, such as an ISCC code, ensuring the declaration is tied to a provable source identity.

The architecture is designed to be interoperable with wider EU trust and identity-verification infrastructures, allowing future institutional operators (like the [EUIPO](#)) to assume the role of credential issuer using their own qualified certificates.

Attaching rights owners' preferences to content

The TDM-AI protocol links rights-holders' preferences to specific content using two standards: the International Standard Content Code for asset identification and Creator Credentials to ensure the declarations are genuine and trustworthy. The preference declarations by the rightsholders can be persistently and verifiably associated with individual digital assets via a registry rather than relying solely on domain- or location-based signaling.

The registry can be centralized or federated to function as a persistent database where machine-readable usage preferences are stored and associated with the ISCC codes. This infrastructure is necessary to enable the discovery of preferences across diverse distribution channels.

In a federated architecture, the registry operates as a network of certified nodes where various service providers manage onboarding and credential issuance for their respective communities, while a central supervisory entity maintains the core technical infrastructure and coordinates the global trust framework. By linking declarations to verifiable digital fingerprints in this manner, the protocol ensures that AI developers can reliably resolve and respect a creator's intent even if the content has been manipulated or moved.

Source: <https://docs.tdmai.org/>

Who is behind it

The main developer is the Dutch-based company [Liccium B.V.](#), a “rights management platform

that empowers creators and rightsholders with innovative solutions for verifiable content authentication and digital copyright protection.”

Liccium’s founder and leader, Sebastian Posth, is also the co-initiator of ISO 24138:2024 (ISCC – International Standard Content Code).

Development status

Despite originating within the context of the [European Directive 2019/790 \(DSM Directive\)](#), TDM-AI aims to provide an interoperable solution for expressing preferences across international regulatory environments and jurisdictions.

The project’s declared use cases revolve around controlling and conditioning the automated reuse of content for machine learning purposes, which include:

- Declaring opt-outs/reservations: The protocol enables creators and rightsholders to persistently and verifiably attach a reservation, such as a full opt-out, from automated consumption activities
- Signaling consent for AI Training: The system provides a standardized way to declare consent for content to be used for training models and applications of generative AI (including models capable of generating text and images)
- Controlling automated processing (TDM): The broader category of Text and Data Mining (TDM) and general Automated Processing (which includes various downstream activities beyond just training) is a core area addressed by the usage preferences defined within the protocol and related standards (like those developed by the IETF that TDM-AI integrates with)
- Governing specific AI activities: By integrating with standardized vocabularies, the protocol covers categories such as AI Training, Generative AI Training, AI Output, and Search

The TDM-AI protocol contains a first proposal of how the preferences can be expressed using an early draft of the Internet Engineering Task Force’s (IETF) AI-preference vocabulary. This functions as a reference point to illustrate how a domain-based attachment mechanism (as proposed by the IETF) can be translated into a registry-based system.

The [CommonsDB project](#) is implementing a registry on the architecture of TDM-AI, leaving open the possibility to exchange information between the two systems with compatible interfaces. The CommonsDB project, launched in late 2025 and scheduled to finish [in July 2026](#). CommonsDB is a registry for Public Domain and openly licensed works. The project is co-funded by the European Union.

Creative Commons Signals

[Creative Commons \(CC\) Signals](#) is a framework designed as a pact between those who steward data collections and those who reuse them for AI development. The Signals allow stewards to move beyond binary "all or nothing" access by expressing specific criteria that AI developers must meet to reuse content. These signals are intended to be both machine-readable (as a "content usage expression") and human-readable (as a "declaration"). CC describes the effort as "defining manners for machines".

The primary target of Signals is "data stewards": non-profit organizations managing data collected from publicly-shared content (Common Crawl, Software Heritage, LALON, etc) as well as data cooperatives like [MiDATA](#), and for-profit ones, like WordPress/Automattic, Reddit, StackOverflow, etc (Defined in the paper "[Data Governance in Open Source AI](#)" by Open Future Foundation, Open Source Initiative, et al.)

The Signals framework addresses standard categories of machine use defined by the IETF AI Preferences working group, such as Automated Processing, AI Training, Generative AI Training, AI Use, and Search. CC signals are implemented as an extension of IETF AI Preferences, attached to assets via [Robots Exclusion Protocol](#) (robots.txt, defined in [RFC 9309](#);) or standard HTTP Content-Usage headers (like CloudFlare's Crawl Control).

The framework is being designed to operate across different legal systems, leveraging copyright as much as possible without creating new property rights.

The most important use cases for CC signals involve four signal elements centered on the principle of reciprocity:

- **Credit:** This requires the reuser to provide attribution and provenance, such as citing the training dataset or providing a link to the collection as a source in model outputs.
- **Direct contribution:** This facilitates a non-commercial structure for financial or in-kind contributions to support the long-term sustainability of the party declaring the signal.
- **Ecosystem contribution:** This use case is designed to encourage giving back in ways that support the commons as a whole, rather than just the specific declaring party.
- **Open:** This signal indicates that reciprocity is met if the resulting AI models are made open by releasing model weights, code, or datasets for others to build upon.

In the context of the Signals framework, Creative Commons assigns to the data steward the role of expressing criteria for how the data collection may be reused by AI developers. Within this technical framework, the steward acts as the Declaring Party, defined as someone who specifies how a content collection should be used by machines, coordinating among their stakeholders to determine appropriate signals even if they do not hold the copyright for every individual asset in the collection.

Focus on data stewards rather than data owners

Creative Commons' effort is unique for its focus on data stewards rather than rightsholders, like content creators. Data stewardship is defined as a function held by units within private

companies or public institutions that are empowered to initiate, facilitate, and coordinate data collaboration and sharing. The role of these stewards extends beyond simple access control; they are responsible for preparing and maintaining data, reducing friction related to sharing, and protecting the various rights and interests in the data.

Many stewards are public interest institutions, such as libraries, heritage institutions, and research bodies. Their institutional role as collectors and disseminators of knowledge can get in conflict with individual creators and rightowners (as evidenced in the 2025 paper by the Data Provenance Initiative, [Consent in crisis](#)). CC Signals is an attempt to balance the long-term sustainability of collections maintained by data stewards by requiring reciprocal contributions from those who derive value from the data.

Who is behind it

The development of CC Signals is a collaborative effort spearheaded by the Creative Commons organization with the support of its community of industry collectives and the broader creators community.

The CC organization maintains the primary GitHub repository for the "cc-signals" draft proposal. Key personnel identified as authors or researchers in CC's related reporting include Anna Tumadóttir (CEO of Creative Commons), Sarah Hinchliff Pearson, Rebecca Ross, and Jack Hardinges.

CC Signals are designed as a technical extension of the foundational work led by the IETF. CC is building its "content usage expression" code and vocabulary upon the standards currently being developed by IETF contributors.

It's worth mentioning that [Creative Commons contributed](#) to the Really Simple Licensing (RSL) Collective ahead of the RSL 1.0 release to integrate "reciprocity" and "contribution" components into the RSL standard, which mirrors elements of the CC Signals framework.

Broader Community Engagement

- Open Source Initiative (OSI) and Open Future partnered with Creative Commons to co-design data governance frameworks for AI, convening experts from the Mozilla Foundation, Open Knowledge Foundation, Common Crawl, and EleutherAI Institute to address the issues of preference signaling.
<https://opensource.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/2025-OSI-DataGovernanceOSAI-final-v5.pdf>
- GitHub contributors: The official [CC signals repository](#) identifies [7 contributors](#) who have submitted commits to the draft proposal.

The project is structured to rely on willing participation from AI developers and feedback from the "broader community" via GitHub issues and discussion threads to establish shared normative ground rules for the AI ecosystem.

Development status

Creative Commons (CC) signals is currently a draft proposal in its prototyping phase. The project has drafted four primary signal elements for public feedback: Credit, Credit + Direct Contribution, Credit + Ecosystem Contribution, and Credit + Open. Development is primarily managed via a GitHub repository, where the community is encouraged to contribute through [Discussions](#) and [Issues](#).

Technically, the framework is being developed as an extension of the IETF AI Preferences Working Group's ongoing work. It specifically builds upon the IETF Vocabulary for Expressing AI Usage Preferences. It utilizes two primary attachment mechanisms: the Robots Exclusion Protocol (robots.txt) for location-based preferences and the HTTP Content-Usage header for unit-based preferences.

Public development seems to have stalled, with the last blog post on the CC site on [Dec 15, 2025](#), and no activity on GitHub for many months (last checked: Mar 6, 2026). Creative Commons suggested a list of activities necessary to complete the Signals:

- **Legal research:** Further analysis of the legal implications and effect of the signals across various global jurisdictions is a major focus for the coming months.
- **Declarations:** CC plans to release a set of human-readable "declarations" that explain the full context of a signal application, including its interaction with copyright status.
- **Best practices:** Future stages of work will include developing guidance and best practices for how AI developers can reasonably adhere to elements such as credit (attribution) and Direct Contribution.
- **Standardization:** The framework is designed to evolve as the IETF finalizes its standard machine-use categories.

Really Simple Licensing (RSL)

[Really Simple Licensing \(RSL\)](#) is a content licensing standard designed specifically to address AI bots and scrapers. It's presented as an evolution of the [Really Simple Syndication \(RSS\)](#) standard that allows publishers to syndicate their content in exchange for traffic. RSL adds machine-readable licensing terms of use to the RSS schema covering all AI use cases. Key aspects of the RSL standard include:

- **Compensation models:** RSL allows publishers to define specific requirements for attribution, as well as commercial terms such as pay per crawl and pay per inference compensation.
- **Automation via Open Licensing Protocol (OLP):** The [RSL Open Licensing Protocol](#) is a "set of Web APIs for acquiring, validating, and enforcing RSL licenses. It replaces proprietary or ad-hoc solutions with a uniform, open protocol for clients and license servers to exchange licensing information using secure HTTPS endpoints. OLP extends the OAuth 2.0 authorization framework [\[RFC 6749\]](#) and related specifications to support machine-readable licensing."
- **Content protection:** The RSL standard replaces ad-hoc integrations with the [Encrypted](#)

[Media Standard \(EMS\)](#), a solution that encrypts and protects proprietary content, such as books, videos, and datasets, during transit.

- Asset catalogs: RSL integrates with RSS and Schema.org, allowing publishers to create standardized, machine-readable catalogs of their licensable digital assets.

To ensure smaller publishers are treated fairly, RSL established the [RSL Collective](#), a non-profit organization. Smaller creators can join the collective for free by signing up directly through their platform. Membership allows creators to collaborate with other content owners to negotiate collective licensing terms, ensuring they receive royalties and proper attribution whenever AI companies use their work. Creators are encouraged to join the [RSL GitHub discussion group](#) to receive the latest updates and share support for the standard on social media. The discussion group doesn't seem to be very active (last posts in September 2025).

Who is behind it

The initiative was launched in September 2025 and is backed by several industry leaders, including Tim O'Reilly (CEO of O'Reilly Media), Neil Vogel (CEO of People Inc.), Simon Wistow (Co-founder of Fastly), Ricky Arai-Lopez (Head of Product at Quora.)

The development of the RSL standard seems to be guided by the RSL Technical Steering Committee. Current members of the TSC are:

- Eckart Walther, Chair, co-creator RSS, RSL Collective
- R.V. Guha, Co-creator RSS, Schema.org
- Andrew Odewahn, O'Reilly Media
- Stephane Koenig, Yahoo
- James LePage, Automattic
- Simon Wistow, Fastly
- Joey Fortuna, Ziff Davis
- Chris Chen, Condé Nast

with input from a broad community of publishers, platforms, and open standards organizations. Public discussions seem to have stopped (last checked the repositories and forums: Feb 26, 2026).

Development status

The standard is hosted on [GitHub](#). Since the initial launch in late Q3 2025, there hasn't been much traffic on the discussion group nor on the repository of the standard itself.

There are some projects on GitHub referencing the standard: The [RSL Editor](#) and an alpha version of a [WordPress plugin](#). Both of these projects have had no activity for months (last checked: Feb 10, 2026).

AI Preference Attachment for Software Projects

The [AI Preference "Attachment" for Software Projects \(Vendoring-Resilient Proposal\)](#) represents a specialized technical framework designed to ensure that a creator's intent regarding AI usage survives the complex lifecycle of source code. The proposal advocates for embedding authoritative signals directly within individual files to ensure they're persistently attached to the code through various distribution channels. In this sense, this approach is similar to TDM-AI's. This framework is designed to be vocabulary-agnostic, meaning it can map its short registry codes to broader standards currently being developed by the IETF AI Preferences Working Group and Creative Commons. By mirroring the successful [REUSE](#) and [SPDX](#) initiatives, it aims to lower the friction for developers to assert control over their copyright in the AI era.

The proposal is being developed within the [CodeCommons](#) project, funded by the French government. CodeCommons' objective is to use the [Software Heritage archive](#) to create the traceable and qualified information necessary to develop ethical and transparent AI training datasets.

The challenge of "vendoring"

The AI Preference for Software Project proposal defines "vendoring" as the pervasive practice of copying files or subtrees across different software projects, identified as a primary obstacle to coherent AI preference signaling.

While this practice is allowed by Open Source licenses, it causes loss of context. Traditional directory-level metadata is often dropped during repackaging, path changes, or inclusion of code in other Open Source packages. Shuffling files and directories while copying them into different repositories damages hierarchical resolution (root → directory → file): modifications to file locations can unintentionally change the governing policy or render it unresolvable once separated from its parent directory.

Core attachment mechanisms

The framework proposes a three-tiered approach to attaching preferences, prioritizing the file-level over the project-level:

- Per-file header tags: The most resilient method involves a single, comment-style line in the file header: `AI-preferences: <CODE>=<BOOL>[; <CODE>=<BOOL> ...]`. This line references a short code from a public registry, ensuring the intent is portable and verifiable by automated linters.
- Sidecar files: For non-commentable formats, such as binaries or specific JSON files, an in-repository sidecar file serves as the authoritative alternative.
- Project-level defaults: A project may include an `AI-preferences.toml` file at the root to provide defaults for unannotated files. However, these defaults aren't expected to travel with single-file copies or vendored subdirectories and therefore aren't safe to be considered authoritative.

Implementation and Builder Behavior

To maintain simplicity and prevent fragmentation, CodeCommons' proposal rejects free-form logic in file headers. Instead, it relies on a public, versioned registry similar to the REUSE and SPDX models used for software licenses compliance.

The proposal simplifies the "builder" or "crawler" logic by removing the need for complex merge rules. For any given file, the system checks for a header tag first; if none exists, it looks for a root default; if neither is present, the status is unspecified. By default, unspecified means free for all uses, because of the particular nature of Open Source software allows unrestricted permissions to be safely assumed. Version 1.1 of the specification introduces a multi-policy syntax that allows for granular code/value pairs separated by semicolons (e.g., AI-preferences: train-ai=n; search=y). The group continues discussing how best to align the logic to the IETF AI-Pref vocabulary.

Who is behind it

The CodeCommons project is a collaborative initiative built on the foundation of Software Heritage and funded by the French government, via the France 2030 program and the French public investment bank BPI. It involves several institutional partners, research teams, and technical organizations.

Development status

The proposal is actively developed. Key contributors listed in the GitLab repository are Roberto di Cosmo and Felix Reda.

Cloudflare AI Crawl Control

[Cloudflare AI Crawl Control](#) is a service that enables website owners to monitor and control how AI services access their online content. Effectively acting as a firewall, it provides visibility into which specific AI services are crawling content, letting content owners filter access starting at the domain level.

AI Crawl Control can analyze incoming traffic, tracking the total number of requests to crawl websites from common AI crawlers and the number of requests made by each AI crawler. The tool can help discover which pages are most frequently requested by AI crawlers.

Cloudflare's tool offers the options to allow or block requests to access content and a third option, in beta, to charge for access. The mechanism is based on HTTP response codes. Each time an AI crawler requests content, it either presents payment intent via request headers for successful access ([HTTP response code 200](#)) or receives a 402 Payment Required [response](#)

with pricing. Cloudflare acts as the Merchant of Record for pay-per-crawl and also provides the underlying technical infrastructure.

Publishers can currently define a flat price across their entire site while retaining the flexibility to bypass charges for specific crawlers as needed. This is particularly helpful if you want to allow a certain crawler through for free, or if you want to negotiate and execute a content partnership outside the pay-per-crawl feature.

Crawler operators and content owners must configure pay-per-crawl payment details in their Cloudflare account. Billing events are recorded each time a crawler makes an authenticated request with payment intent and receives an HTTP 200-level response with a **crawler-charged** header. Cloudflare then aggregates all the events, charges the crawler, and distributes the earnings to the publisher.

Who is behind it

AI Crawl Control is a Cloudflare product, and the company retains full control of its development.

Development status

Cloudflare launched the AI Crawl Control in July 2025. It acts as a stronger enforcement mechanism for robots.txt because, as a firewall, it can effectively prevent crawlers from accessing blocked portions of web assets. It also provides an option for monetization that robots.txt doesn't provide. The company recognizes that the features will need to evolve based on how users adapt to the changes in the AI/ML landscape.

The firewall-based approach inherits some of the limitations of the robots.txt. AI Crawl Control operates at the domain level, making it appealing for publishers while not solving the issue of tracking downstream circulation of downloaded data. For publishers of material licensed under permissive conditions, the AI Crawl Control may not be adequate, as it provides no mechanism to attach preferences to the content itself.

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The landscape of preference signaling for AI training

ACTIVELY DEVELOPED
STALLED
GENERALLY AVAILABLE